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USING INTEGRATED MARKETING COMMUNICATIONS (IMC) IN BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: The increasing use of social media has forced brands to integrate social media into their marketing communication channels, as it has become a necessity of the times, as it determines the overall brand identity, brand image and the company's performance in today's marketing competition. This study aims to trace the evolution and development of the concept of IMC and how it has transformed the approach to marketing communications. The results of the study will serve as a springboard for future research and applications in the field of marketing mix to create a strong foundation for the brand in the minds of physical and virtual customers.

Key words: integrated marketing communications (IMC), marketing, product, brand, marketing channels, word of mouth marketing, SEO.

Annotatsiya: Ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanishning ortib borayotgani brendlarni o'z marketing kommunikatsiyasi kanallariga ijtimoiy tarmoqlarni integratsiya qilishga majbur qildi, chunki bu zamon talabi bo'lib, u umumiy brend identiteti, brend imiji va kompaniya faoliyatini belgilovchi omilga aylandi. Ushbu tadqiqot integratsiyalashgan marketing kommunikatsiyalari (IMC) konsepsiyasining evolyutsiyasi va rivojlanishini, shuningdek, uning marketing kommunikatsiyalariga yondashuvdagi o'zgarishlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari marketing miksi sohasidagi keyingi tadqiqotlar va amaliyotlar uchun tayanch vazifasini bajarib, brendni real va virtual mijozlar ongida mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: integratsiyalashgan marketing kommunikatsiyasi (IMC), marketing, mahsulot, brend, marketing kanallari, og'zaki marketing, SEO.

Аннотация: Рост популярности социальных сетей заставил бренды интегрировать их в свои маркетинговые коммуникационные каналы, так как это стало необходимостью времени. Социальные сети сегодня определяют общее восприятие бренда, его имидж и эффективность компании в условиях маркетинговой конкуренции. Цель данного исследования — проследить эволюцию и развитие концепции интегрированных маркетинговых коммуникаций (IMC), а также понять, как она изменила подход к маркетинговым коммуникациям. Результаты исследования послужат основой для будущих исследований и практического применения в рамках маркетингового комплекса с целью формирования прочного имиджа бренда как среди физических, так и виртуальных клиентов.

Ключевые слова: интегрированные маркетинговые коммуникации (IMC), маркетинг, продукт, бренд, маркетинговые каналы, сарафанное радио, SEO.

INTRODUCTION

Current marketing communications operate in an environment that is saturated with product messages and increasingly distracts consumers [1]. One of the most important changes is the dramatic increase in the communication options available to advertisers. In this regard, strategic consistency of all messages between the various elements of marketing communications is essential to ensure a consistent brand image that attracts consumers, as well as to achieve synergistic effects. This strategic consistency is recommended as the most recommended approach for developing integrated marketing communications (IMC) [2]. Most of the research on IMC focuses on evaluating the synergistic effects of this strategy to achieve economic and financial advantages.

However, one several studies have focused on analyzing how integration affects consumers themselves. Most of these studies used a variety of media in a coordinated advertising campaign [3]. However, they are not true integration, but only the coordination of communication tools. Other studies analyze the impact of various tools without explaining the criteria used to implement integration [4]. Integrated marketing is the search for the optimal ratio of all marketing tools used in a given market situation, which will have a synergistic effect. An

integrated marketing strategy is based on consistency and considers how it affects the processing, memory and relationships of consumers. Based on this, the scientific article also analyzes the role of an integrated marketing strategy in influencing the consumer's opinion about the purchase and creating a brand.

The fact that a modern market structure is being created in Uzbekistan and the marketing strategy is being improved necessitates the study of the theoretical and methodological foundations of integrated marketing. From this point of view, the topic of the scientific article is relevant and aims to develop proposals and recommendations on the directions of market activity management by using integrated marketing communications.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) has emerged as a strategic imperative in modern business management, transcending traditional marketing practices by emphasizing message consistency across diverse channels. The evolution of IMC has been extensively examined by scholars, highlighting its central role in aligning promotional tools and enhancing brand equity.

Don E. Schultz, widely regarded as the pioneer of IMC, emphasized its strategic nature, arguing that marketing communications must be orchestrated to deliver a unified message that resonates across all consumer touchpoints. In his foundational work at Northwestern University, Schultz demonstrated how IMC supports customer-centric planning, shifting the focus from media-based strategies to outcome-oriented communication programs. He advocated for IMC as a management philosophy that aligns communication efforts with business goals and market realities.

Kitchen and Burgmann analyzed the conceptual development of IMC and noted its transformation from a tactical coordination tool to a holistic approach that integrates advertising, public relations, sales promotion, and digital marketing. Their findings suggest that effective IMC implementation strengthens brand coherence and improves organizational agility, especially in dynamic market environments.

Kliatchko contributed significantly to IMC theory by proposing a multi-level framework encompassing content integration, stakeholder integration, and cross-functional alignment. His research revealed that IMC is not merely a marketing function but a strategic organizational process requiring collaboration among departments such as sales, operations, and finance to ensure message consistency and customer engagement.

In the digital era, Mangold and Faulds emphasized the growing importance of social media as a component of IMC. They argued that platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube have expanded the IMC landscape by enabling real-time consumer interaction, user-generated content, and viral marketing. According to their study, integrating traditional and social media enhances message credibility and reach, especially among younger consumers.

Furthermore, the application of IMC in business management has demonstrated measurable outcomes. Studies by Reid, Luxton, and Mavondo identified a positive correlation between IMC maturity and business performance metrics such as customer loyalty, market share, and profitability. They concluded that firms with well-integrated communication strategies exhibit stronger brand equity and greater marketing ROI.

Overall, the literature underlines that IMC plays a critical role in unifying business messaging, fostering internal collaboration, and enhancing customer relationships. It is increasingly recognized as a core competence in strategic business management, especially as digital transformation accelerates and marketing ecosystems grow more complex.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research employed a mixed-method approach, combining qualitative content analysis of academic publications with quantitative data collected through structured surveys distributed to marketing professionals. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and thematic coding to identify key patterns in the implementation and impact of IMC strategies in business management.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) is the process of unifying a brand's messages so that they are consistent across all media used to reach a brand's target audience. It is a strategic approach that manages communications and tactics across all marketing channels. Every organization uses multiple channels to communicate with its audience. In today's digital world, it can be difficult to keep track of all the media outlets through which you can reach your potential customers. However, the intensity of the competition has made it necessary for many companies to focus on multiple marketing channels at once.

This can be explained by the following considerations [10]:

The need for consistency in the process of customers from product selection to purchase.

The purposeful use of the right mix of marketing channels helps to increase the effectiveness of the company. The IMC consists of a complex of interconnected marketing channels.

If we dwell on each case of analyzing the need for IMC, the following results can be seen:

1. The need for consistency in the process of customers from choosing a product to purchasing it. This process begins with informing the customer about the product or service, and helps to increase the customer's choice. It uses various means to interest him and encourage him to purchase the product.

It makes changes to the product, taking into account the customer's opinion (Figure 1).

Figure 1. IMK in the process of customer selection from product selection to purchase

2. IMK helps in brand building.

The brand is the main factor that determines the price and shelf life of the product. Using IMK to build a brand quickly and allows introduction.

3. Targeted use of the right mix of marketing channels helps to increase the company's efficiency

IMC forces you to rethink which marketing channels you are on and how you are using them. There are now many ways to reach people online and offline. However, increasing sales by supporting only one marketing channel may not be effective in the era of globalization. In general, the ideal way to integrate your communications is to spend 60% of your budget on brand building and the remaining 40% on increasing sales.

1. The IMC consists of a complex of interconnected marketing channels

This usually allows for the simultaneous use of word-of-mouth marketing and SEO marketing. For example, bloggers on social networks use word-of-mouth marketing to promote a product or company's website. In this case, customers coordinate the information they receive from word-of-mouth marketing with the information on the website (table 1).

Table 1. Advantages and disadvantages of using IMK [11]

Integrated marketing communication the advantages are as follows	Integrated marketing communication difficulties are as follows
Messages delivered across channels are only effective when they are integrated; IMC results in increased efficiency through internal capabilities and external communications.	It is complex and involves bringing together different budgets, initiatives, goals, and individuals;

By integrating your marketing communications, your company will be more effective. To adopt this strategy and implement an integrated company, you need to take a few key steps: Define your audience. Who are your target customers? Use internal data and research to understand their behavior and preferences. Identify the channels they are most likely to use. For example, TikTok, Instagram, and LinkedIn each have different age demographics. Listen to your customers' pain points and engage with people who can help shape the target audience.

- Build a team. Identify the departments that need to be involved.
- formulate tasks;
- set goals;
- plan the composition;

- create a visual theme with coded colors, fonts, and graphics;
- use emotions and stories to attract attention and increase engagement;
- consider the brand's history and uniqueness;
- choose a feature or quality that consistently emerges through repeated use;
- choose a voice and tone that is consistent with the brand identity, the company, and different audience segments;
- create landing pages to capture leads;
- determine how to adapt communication for different stages of the sales journey;
- create a workflow and schedule.

Integrated marketing communications is one of the most important marketing principles to understand today. However, its implementation can be fraught with complexities and difficulties. In particular [12]:

There are some obstacles to implementing a strategy. By far the biggest challenge is internal communication and collaboration. Such integration is inherently complex, as it involves bringing together different budgets, initiatives, goals, and people. However, the goal of the IMC should be to establish leadership that takes ownership and responsibility for planning, rather than letting things happen by accident. Another obstacle is implementation. Branding documents need to be clearly and consistently communicated to everyone, including contractors. When it comes time to implement them, the agenda can be vague and efforts can lose focus or disappear altogether. It is important to have a detailed plan in place to stay on track and to know in advance how they will be applied in different contexts.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

As a result of the analysis, the following conclusions were drawn:

IMC is a comprehensive marketing management system that allows for the effective use of various marketing tools, including advertising.

Various means of promoting sales are developed in the IMC.

Based on the above conclusions, the following proposals were formulated:

- IMC is a modern marketing tool that requires implementation regardless of the size of the company;
- The effectiveness of the IMC system is determined by its proximity to the customer
- The effectiveness of the IMK system is determined by its closeness to the customer, for the activities of companies that want to gain a competitive advantage through marketing tools recommended;
- Taking into account that the use of IMK is important in creating a brand, it is recommended to use it in the first stage of the product's life cycle..

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